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Integrating Forensic Accounting Skills into Business Education Curriculum for Enhanced Postgraduate Business Education Students' Employability in in Rivers State.

¹Peter Clinton Ogwunte, Ph.D & ²James-Ngochindo Peace Ph.D

Department of Business Education,

Faculty of Education,

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

¹E-mail: peter.ogunte@ust.edu.ng/Tel: 08033446792

²E-mail: peace.james_ngochindo@ust.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to integrate forensic accounting into Business Education curriculum for enhanced postgraduate Business Education students' employability in Rivers State. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consist of 41 Business Education Lecturers from two universities offering Business Education programme in Rivers State. These universities are Rivers State Universities (RSU = 30) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE = 11). The entire population was studied as sample size, because the population was manageable. A self –structured instrument titled “Integration of Forensic Account in Business Education Curriculum Questionnaire (IFABECQ)” was the main instrument used for data collection. The instrument was designed on a four point rating scale with options: Very High Extent (VHE – 4points), High Extent (HE – 3points), Moderate Extent (ME – 2points) and Low Extent (LE – 1point) respectively. The validation of the instrument was done by three experts, two in Business Education and one in measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha Statistics. The computation yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.92. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses was tested with t-test statistics. The findings reveal that Integration of investigative accounting skills and litigation services skills in Business Education Curriculum would enhance Postgraduate Business Education students employability to a high extent. Based on the findings, the researchers amongst others recommended that forensic accounting courses should be integrated into Business Education curriculum to equip students with investigative accounting and litigation skills

Keywords: Business Education, Curriculum integration, Forensic Account, Employability and Postgraduate students.

INTRODUCTION

The world of business has become increasingly complex, with the rise of financial crimes, fraud and other irregularities posing significant threats to organizations and economies. In response to these challenges, the demand for skilled professionals who can detect and prevent financial crimes has grown

exponentially, leading to the demand for forensic accountants. Forensic accounting involves accounting, auditing and analytical skills to conduct an inspection into a company's financial statement (Gupta, 2022). It is basically the application of accounting knowledge, principles, methods, interpersonal skills and analytical skills to look beyond the numbers to detect various offenses and frauds in the books of accounts. For Olukayode (2018), forensic accounting is the application of auditing, accounting, statistics, research and economic concepts and techniques to investigation with the sole aim of solving a legal problem or potential problem in form of bribery, fraud, embezzlement, corruption, and forgery that may occur from the economic or financial transactions. Al-Sharairi (2018) viewed forensic accounting as a homogeneous mixture that links accounting, auditing and judiciary through a legal point of view to present a report that contributes in solving arguments and disputes.

Forensic accounting combines investigative, accounting and auditing skills while applying accounting facts and concepts discovered through auditing methodologies, strategies and procedures to resolve legal and associated difficulties (Okoye, Nwoge, Akachi & Onyema, 2020). In the context of this study, forensic accounting is defined by the authors as the science that combines auditing, investigative and accounting competencies to unveil fraudulent incidents and produce proof that are tenable in the Court of Law. The discussion so far revealed that the definition of forensic accounting varies from author to author; however, all the definitions contain similar core ideas and can be summarized as “Accounting Techniques Intended for a Court.” (Huber, 2012). For the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE) (2022), forensic accounting involves the use of professional accounting skills in matter involving potential or actual civil or criminal litigations, including, but not limited to generally acceptable accounting and audit principles, the determination of lost profits, income, assets or damages, evaluation of internal controls, fraud and any other matter involving accounting expertise in the legal system. The objectives of forensic accounting includes: assessment of damages caused by an auditors negligence, fact-finding to see whether an embezzlement has been in place, in what amount and whether criminal proceedings are to be initiated. With the computation of asset values in a divorce proceedings (Bhasing, 2013).

Forensic accounting faces several challenges, especially in its actual practices. Such as the lack of forensic accounting standards that accountants can use or refer to when acting as expert witnesses for litigation consultants. Significant dearth of experienced financial accountants, limited social awareness about the need for forensic accounting in the general society and academic sector and lack of national level training opportunities to advance the analytical and communication skills deemed crucial for financial accountants (Ramadhan, 2015). The efficacy of forensic accounting in detecting and preventing financial crimes hinges on the ability of forensic accountants to navigate complex challenges. This linkage is crucial for researchers and practitioners seeking understanding of the dynamics between challenges and requisite skills in forensic accounting.

Forensic accounting skills refers to the specialized skills and knowledge used to investigate financial crimes, disputes and irregularities. Forensic accountants apply their expertise to analyze financial data, identify potential fraud and provide expert testimony in legal proceedings. For Hassan and Mortaza (2018). The key forensic accounting skills and records to identify anomalies and potential fraud includes the ability to analyse financial statements transactions method and tools used to investigate financial crimes such as data mining and forensic auditing. The researchers also perceived forensic accounting skills to include a strong understanding of accounting principles, standards and practices, familiarity with laws and regulations related to financial crimes such as money laundering and tax evasion, ability to effectively communicate complex financial information to non-accountants including lawyers, judges and juries. From the foregoing, it is that forensic accounting skills provide services in accounting, auditing, investigation, damages claim, analysis, valuation and general consultation and also have critical role in insurance claims, personal claims, fraud claims, construction, auditing of publication right and in detection of terrorism by using financial precedents. However, there are key competences that a forensic accountant should possessed to effectively perform their duties. These include investigative accounting,

litigation support services and computer forensic investigation (Hopwood, 2018). For the purpose of this study, investigative accounting and litigation support service skills would be discussed.

Investigative accounting is a specialized field of accountancy that involves using accounting skills and techniques to investigate financial crimes, disputes and irregularities. Investigative accountants use their expertise to analyse financial data, identify potential risks and provide evidence to support legal proceedings (Singleton, 2018). The key activities of investigative accounting includes; analysing financial statements, transactions and records to identify potential irregularities or crimes (Moroney, 2019), using accounting and investigative techniques to detect and prevent financial crimes such as fraud and embezzlement (KPMG, 2020), analysing digital evidence such as emails and computer files to identify potential financial crime (Carrier, 2019), providing expert testimony in court to explain complex financial concepts and supports legal proceedings (Kessler, 2019). A CFE (2022) reported that fraud investigation accounting can be applied to investigate allegations of financial fraud such as embezzlement, bribery and money laundering. For Kessler (2019), fraud investigation accounting is applied to provide expert analysis and testimony in financial disputes such as breach of contract and intellectual property disputes.

Investigative accounting skills play a crucial role in uncovering financial crimes, disputes, and irregularities. These skills involve a combination of accounting knowledge, investigative techniques and analytical skills to identify and quantify financial losses or irregularities (Singleton, 2018). Investigative accountants use various techniques, including financial statement analysis, forensic accounting and digital forensics to detect and prevent financial crime. This implies that financial crime can have significant consequences for organizations such as financial loss, reputational damage and legal liability (ACFE, 2022). Investigative accountants use their skills to identify and analyze financial transactions, identify patterns and anomalies, and provide evidence to support legal proceedings (Moroney, 2019). Investigative accountants also play a key role in detecting and preventing financial irregularities such as accounting errors or misstatements (PCAOB, 2020). They use their skills to identify potential risks and provide recommendations for improvement (IFAC, 2019).

Litigation Support Service Skills play a vital role in assisting legal professionals in dispute resolution. These skills involve a combination of technical knowledge, analytical skills, and communication expertise to provide expert support in litigation cases (Kessler, 2019). Litigation support professionals use various techniques, including financial analysis, data analysis and expert testimony to help resolve complex disputes (Moroney, 2019). Singleton (2018) stated that some of the skills required for litigation support service includes analyzing financial data to identify patterns, anomalies and potential damages, analysing large datasets to identify relevant information and patterns, providing expert testimony in court to explain complex financial concepts and support litigation cases (Bala, 2020), and communicating complex financial information effectively to legal professionals, judges and juries (Hildebrand, 2019).

In the application of litigation support services, Kessler (2019) noted that expert analysis and testimony can be provided in commercial disputes such as breach of contracts and intellectual property disputes. Also, ACFE (2022) reported that litigation support service can be used to assist in the investigation and prosecution of financial crimes such as fraud and embezzlement, and in providing expert analysis and testimony in intellectual property disputes such as patent and trademark infringement cases. There are several benefits to the acquisition of litigation support service skills. Kessler (2019) reported that litigation support professionals can help resolve disputes more efficiently and effectively by providing expert analysis and testimony. Expert testimony from litigation support professionals can enhance the credibility of a successful outcome (Moroney et al, 2019), litigation support professionals can help streamline the litigation process by identifying and analysing relevant financial data and providing expert analysis (Singleton, 2018). These skills are essential in Business Education programme.

Business Education is an essential part of the general education which continuously builds upon the knowledge, skills, values and attitudes of education and obviously a form of that education that has great prospect for Nigerian economy. Business Education is an aspect of the general education that involves the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in the industry as well as the classrooms. In the view of Mansueto Ventures (2021), Business Education is a

term that encompasses a number of methods used to teach students the fundamentals of business practices. Business Education as a branch of vocational education equips its recipients with relevant skills needed in the world of work.

According to Olagunju (2020), Business Education is a branch of education that involves teaching the skills and operations of the business industry. Makinwa (2019), defined Business Education as education that prepares youth and adult for employment by providing experience which enables them to develop competencies needed in the job. For Ekole, Nweke and Offia (2019), Business Education is a course that prepares students for life in the business world. Similarly, the authors defined business education as a structured and organized instructional programme designed to convey knowledge, skills, ideas, attitudes and technical expertise to individuals, equipping them for application in both business environment and for instructing others. With the knowledge of business education, students are better informed and ground with skills and understanding to cope with the unpredictable challenges of the business environment. Supporting this assertion, Imeokpara (2020), affirmed that the value of any Business Education programme can be assessed by its capacity to effectively prepare individuals, enabling them to excel in specific roles, remain technologically up-to-date, compete on a global scale, and achieve economic prosperity when appropriately packaged and delivered. Yet, the dependable means by which Business Education programmes can realize its mission and vision lies in the thorough review and successful implementation of curriculum.

Curriculum is an embodiment of all knowledge, skills and attitudes which a nation, through her schools, imparts to her citizens, generalizations and rules needed to be acquired to be certified as competent in a field. Curriculum also involves the acquisition of skills needed to perform tasks programming for effective teaching and learning. In actual sense, a curriculum is an educational programme without which education could hardly be organized. According to Igbe (2016) in Ogwunte (2023), Curriculum is an orderly collection of obligatory, essential and vital subjects included in a specific course or programme for studies in a school, college or university." Mikpa and Smuchi (2009) view curriculum as a vehicle through which the school could strive towards the achievement of educational ends. Such ends could be those of the nation, state and local government or communities. A curriculum could also be considered as the deliberate systematic and planned attempts made by the school to change the behaviour of the members of the society in which it situates, in the views of the authors, curriculum encompasses the content to be studied, its organization, the methods of teaching and learning, and the evaluation of student progress. Thus, Business Education curriculum, is a set of learning experience designed to enable students attain the objective of business education. From the discussion so far, it is clear that the curriculum of Business Education exposes students to educational and business-related experience. Omoejiofor (2020), reported that the curriculum of Business Education offerings at the tertiary institutions do not align with some of the current century's skills requirements. Gidado and Akaeze (2014) concurred by highlighting that Business Education in Nigeria does not align with the global digital world. This incongruity underscores a significant gap between what universities provide and what the labour market demands. The challenge at hand is to bridge this gap by ensuring that a curriculum and delivery methods produce graduates who can compete effectively in the global job market. To achieve this goal, it is imperative for postgraduate Business Education student to be trained on requisite forensic accounting skills to enhance their employability in the world of work.

Postgraduate Business Education students are individuals that are pursuing advanced degrees in business education programme such as Masters of Education (M.Ed), Masters of Science in Education (M.Sc) and Doctor of Philosophy in all options of Business Education (Ph.D) such Accounting, Management Office and Management Technology, Marketing and Entrepreneurship (Kune & Bhandari, 2017). These students are typically motivated by a desire to enhance their career prospects, develop their skills and knowledge, and increase their earning potentials.

Employability is a critical concern for postgraduate Business Education students as they seek to secure jobs in competitive markets and advance their careers (Edison, 2021). Employability refers to the ability of an individual to gain and maintain employment, as well as adapt to a changing job market requirement.

It is a multifaceted concept that encompasses various skills, knowledge and personal attributes. Employability is linked to acquiring skills for life, including communication, numeracy, information technology and learning how to learn. These skills are essential for future success, regardless of career path.

Statement of Problem

The relationship between the quality of skills acquired by Business Education postgraduate students and the world of work has been the focus of growing theoretical and empirical investigations in education literature. The employers' view of how well business education graduate students are prepared for the workplace have received widespread attention in the education sector. The design of business education is based on a vision and a set of competencies planned to prepare students to be knowledgeable and ethical decision-makers as they fulfill their roles as consumers, workers, good citizens, and also contribute to the development of the nation. However, observation has shown that forensic accounting skills has not been extensively integrated into Business Education programmes of Rivers State universities.

Given that this is so, the question is put: What are the investigative and litigation support service skills needed for postgraduate Business Education students employability in Rivers State? To address this question, there is a need to empirically study and ascertain the forensic accounting skills required for enhanced postgraduate Business Education students' employability in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does the integration of investigative accounting skills in Business Education curriculum enhance postgraduate Business Education students' employability in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does the integration of litigation support service skills in Business Education curriculum enhance postgraduate Business Education students' employability in Rivers State?

Purpose of the study

The general purpose of the study is to enhance postgraduate Business Education students' employability in Rivers State through the integration of Forensic Accounting Skills. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent to which the integration of investigative accounting skills in Business Education Curriculum enhance postgraduate Business Education students' employability in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the extent to which integration of Litigation Support Service skills in Business Education Curriculum enhance postgraduate Business Education students' employability in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and Rivers State University (RSU) Business Education Lecturers on the extent to which the integration of investigative accounting skills in Business Education curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Education employability in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and Rivers State University (RSU) Business Education Lecturers on the extent to which the integration of Litigation Support Service skills in Business Education curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Education students employability in Rivers State.

METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 41 Business Education Lecturers from two universities offering Business Education Programme in Rivers State. These universities are Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE = 11) and Rivers State University (RSU=30). The entire population was studied because the population was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a self-made questionnaire titled "Forensic Accounting skills required for employability questionnaire (FASREQ)". The questionnaire was divided into two parts, A and B. Part

A was designed to collect demographic information of respondents, while Part B was designed on a 4-point rating scaled of High Extent (HE – 4 points), Moderate Extent (ME – 3 points), Low Extent (LE – 2points) and very low Extent (VLE – 1point) respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts, one in Measurement and Evaluation and two from Business Education Department, all from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The Cronbach Alpha statistic was used to computer data collected from the pilot study conducted which yielded reliability co-efficient value of 0.78. The researchers personally distributed copies of the instruments with the help of two research assistants adequately briefed. Data generated were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and homogeneity boundary mean score of 2.50. A cluster with mean score equal to or above 2.50 was regardless high extent, while the one with mean score less than 2.50 was rated as low extent. T-text was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated value of t is less than the significant level of 0.05 and rejected if the calculated valued is equal to or greater than the significant level of 0.05.

ANALYSIS OF DATA AND RESULT

Research Questions 1: *To what extent does the integration of investigate accounting skills into Business Education Curriculum enhance postgraduate skills into Business Education Students employability in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean Responses of IAUE and RSU Business Education Lecturers on the extent, integration of Investigative Accounting skills in Business Education Curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Education Students employability.

S/N	Items – Statements	\bar{X}	IAUE n = 11 SD	Remarks	\bar{X}	RSU n = 30 SD	Remarks
1	Apply investigative accounting techniques to detect financial fraud	3.84	0.76	High Extent	3.51	1.13	High Extent
2	Understand how to analyse financial statements for signs of irregularities	3.84	0.83	High Extent	3.87	0.39	High Extent
3	Gather and analyse evidence for legal proceedings	3.84	0.81	High Extent	3.68	1.38	High Extent
4	Understand how to preserved and document evidence for investigation	3.84	0.66	High Extent	3.62	0.74	High Extent
5	Conduct interview and gather information from witnesses and suspects	3.84	0.66	High Extent	3.87	0.38	High Extent
	Grand \bar{x} & SD	3.78	0.74	High Extent	3.62	0.80	High Extent

Source: Survey Data (2025)

The data in table 1 shows that the integration of investigative accounting skill in Business Education Curriculum can enhance Postgraduate Business Education students employability to a high extent. This is evident in the aggregate mean of 3.78 for Rivers State University and 3.62 for Ignatius Ajuru University of Education respectively.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does the integration of litigation support service skills in Business Education curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Education students employability in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean Responses of IAUE and RSU Business Education Lecturers on the extent integration of litigation support service enhance Postgraduate Business Education students employability.

S/N	Items – Statements	\bar{X}	IAUE n = 11 SD	Remarks	\bar{X}	RSU n = 30 SD	Remarks
1	Understand the role of litigation support in legal proceedings	4.0	0.56	High Extent	3.51	1.13	High Extent
2	Can assist in managing and analyzing large datasets for litigation purposes.	3.93	0.41	High Extent	3.51	1.38	High Extent
3	Know how to identify and preserve relevant documents and evidences	3.75	0.67	High Extent	3.62	0.71	High Extent
4	Can conduct data analysis and create reports for litigation support	3.75	0.72	High Extent	3.56	1.13	High Extent
5	Understand how to manage document review and coding processes	3.71	0.98	High Extent	3.56	0.45	High Extent
Grand \bar{x} & SD		3.82	0.66	High Extent	3.55	0.96	High Extent

Source: Survey Data (2025)

Data presented in Table 2 revealed that the integration of litigation support service skills in Business Education curriculum can enhance Postgraduate Business Education Students employability to a High Extent. This is evident in the grand mean of 3.82 for Rivers State University and 3.55 for Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and Rivers State University (RSU) Business Education Lecturers on the extent to which the integration of investigative accounting skills in Business Education curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Education Students employability in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis on the extent, IAUE and RSU Business Education Lecturers perceive Investigative Accounting skills for enhancing employability skills of Postgraduate Students.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	α	std error	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
IAUE	11	3.78	0.74	39	0.05	0.276	0.58	1.96	Accepted
RSU	30	3.62	0.80						

Source: Survey Data (2025)

Data presented in Table 3 showed the t-calculated value of 0.58 at 39 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated t-value of 0.58 is less than the t-critical (t-crit) of 1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and Rivers State University (RSU) Business Education Lecturers on the extent to which the integration

of Litigation Support Service skills in Business Education curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Education Students employability in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis on the extent to which IAUE and RSU Lecturers perceive Litigation support service skills for Enhancing Employability skills of Postgraduate Business Education students.

Variables category	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	α	std error	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
IAUE	11	3.82	0.66	39	0.05	0.3135	0.86	1.96	Accepted
RSU	30	3.55	0.96						

Source: Survey Data (2025)

Data presented in Table 3 showed the t-calculated value of 0.86 at 39 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated t-value of 0.86 is less than the t-critical (t-crit) of 1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result for research question one of the study revealed the extent integration of investigative accounting skills into Business Education Curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Education students employability in Rivers State.

The result showed that Business Educators in Rivers State Universities agreed that integration of investigative accounting skills into Business Education Curriculum would enhance postgraduate business education students employability to a High Extent. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Kessler (2019) and Godspower (2021)who submitted that fraud investigative skills enables forensic accountants to provide expertise testimony in court to explain complex financial concepts and support legal proceedings. This implies that the integration of investigative skills in Business Education curriculum will equip Postgraduate students with investigative skills. The researchers also support the above finding by stating that the integration of investigative accounting skills in Business Education Curriculum would enable Postgraduate students to maintain financial integrity and trust thereby preparing them to apply investigative accounting skills in the real world scenarios. The corresponding hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of IAUE and RSU Business Education Lecturers on the extent to which the integration of investigative accounting skills into Business Education Curriculum enhance Postgraduate Business Student employability.

The result from research question two also showed extent integration of litigation support service skills into Business Education curriculum enhance postgraduate Business Education Students employability in Rivers State. The result revealed that Business Educators in Rivers State Universities agreed that integration of litigation support service skills into Business Education Curriculum would enhance Postgraduate Business Education Students employability to a High Extent. This finding corroborates the findings of ACFE (2022) and Chukwugbo (2014), who reported that litigation support service can be used to assist in the investigation and prosecution of financial crimes such as fraud and embezzlement, and in providing expert analysis and testimony in intellectual property disputes such as patent right and infringement cases. The researchers also submit that effective litigation support can significantly impact the outcome of legal proceedings hence, the need for integration of litigation service in Business Education programme.

CONCLUSION

Integrating forensic accounting skills into Business Educations curriculum would enhance student’s employability by equipping them with specialized knowledge in investigative accounting and litigation support services. These skills are increasingly in demand as businesses and legal professionals seeks experts who can detect and prevent financial crimes, provide litigation support and ensure financial

integrity. By incorporating forensic accounting into curriculum, educational institutions can better prepare students for their complexities of the modern business environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researchers recommended that:

1. Forensic accounting courses should be integrated into Business Education Curriculum to equip students with Investigative accounting and litigation support skills.
2. Rivers State Universities should develop practical training programme that include real-world case studies, e-discovery tools and data analysis software.

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